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PFA RECONSTRUCTION ALGORITHMS

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Abstract:

We summarise the developments that have been made in Particle Flow Algorithms (PFAs) for reconstructing particles using the Pandora software framework for three next-generation detector topics: the emerging technology of dual-readout calorimeters; improving the reconstruction of hadronic jets for the future linear collider; and using new 3D-readout liquid argon detectors for the Deep Underground Neutrino Experiment (DUNE).

AIDAinnova Consortium, 2024

For more information on AIDAinnova, its partners and contributors please see <http://aidainnova.web.cern.ch/>

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Executive summary

This report summarises the research outcomes for adding state-of-the-art Particle Flow Algorithms (PFAs) into the Pandora software toolkit for three main detector themes, namely: the promising technology of dual-readout calorimeters for the Future Circular Collider (FCC-ee); improving the reconstruction of hadronic jets for the future International Linear Collider (ILC); and using new 3D-readout technology for liquid argon (LAr) detectors in neutrino experiments. For the topic of dual-readout calorimeters, an attempt was made to develop a machine-learning algorithm that completely reconstructs particle jets, thereby improving their energy resolution. However, it was found to be too challenging, and already established traditional reconstruction methods, such as track fitting, preliminary clustering and matching tracks to clusters, must first be done before neural networks are used to improve the reconstruction. We also report on the research done with APRIL, the algorithm for particle reconstruction (of hadronic jets) for the ILC, which is being developed for the International Large Detector (ILD) semi-digital hadronic calorimeter. This work includes energy calibration studies and developments to include APRIL into the Pandora toolkit. Finally, we describe the research done to develop 3D algorithms for the reconstruction of neutrino interactions in the liquid argon Near Detector (ND-LAr) for the Deep Underground Neutrino Experiment (DUNE), which are available in Pandora's LArRecoND package. This work includes using deep learning to find the neutrino interaction vertices, as well as the implementation of Common Analysis Files (CAF) using hierarchy tools which will be used for DUNE neutrino physics analyses.

INTRODUCTION

Particle flow algorithms (PFAs) are state-of-the-art reconstruction methods for high-energy physics calorimeters and neutrino detectors. These use the Pandora software toolkit [1], which is a general framework that implements a multi-algorithm, step-by-step approach for reconstructing particle interactions, in which more sophisticated methods are deployed as the event picture develops. These algorithms use machine learning networks as well as knowledge about the detector. Pandora is being successfully used to identify neutrino interactions for MicroBooNE [2] and the Short Baseline Neutrino Detector (SBND) [3], as well as studying charged-particle test-beam interactions in the Far Detector prototypes for the Deep Underground Neutrino Experiment (DUNE) [4]. It has also seen notable use for optimisation of detector designs for the International Linear Collider (ILC) [5] and the Compact Linear Collider (CLIC) [6]. The aim of this project is to develop reconstruction algorithms for the Pandora toolkit for three next-generation detector themes: dual-readout calorimeters, hadronic jets for a future linear collider, and 3D-readout technology for liquid argon (LAr) neutrino detectors. This report summarises the work that has been done for these three topics.

2 DUAL-READOUT CALORIMETERS

The new technology of dual-readout calorimeters can improve the energy resolution of hadronic particle showers by measuring their electromagnetic and hadronic components separately using scintillating and Cherenkov fibres. This is being pursued for future circular and linear colliders and is an important component of the IDEA concept (Innovative Detector for future Electron-positron Accelerators) [7]. The Key4hep framework has been used to implement a full Geant4 simulation [8] of the IDEA design, incorporating both the tracking drift chamber and the dual-readout calorimeter, which includes a silicon photomultiplier model that simulates the digitisation of the photon signals from the energy deposits. The conceptual calorimeter design and prototype fibre layout is shown in Fig. 1, and the aim of this research is to build up a neural network (NN) algorithm inside the Pandora

framework which uses the collection of energy deposits in the dual-readout calorimeter to completely reconstruct the jets with improved energy resolution.

Fig. 1 Conceptual design of the dual-readout calorimeter and the layout of its fibres.

2.1 RECONSTRUCTION USING NEURAL NETWORKS

The development workflow first uses Key4hep simulations for the NN training outside of Pandora, then an algorithm within Pandora processes the NN information to create Particle Flow Objects (PFOs) of the reconstructed jets. Two NN approaches were considered: a deep NN (DNN) with 10 or 20 hidden layers and a convolutional NN (CNN) using a visual geometry group (VGG) with multiple layers. The DNN needs more memory than the CNN, and both were investigated using the CPU and GPU installation at the INFN Roma Tre cluster computing centre.

2.1.1 DNN Approach

TensorFlow, interfaced with Keras, was used to build and train the NN using CPUs and GPUs for samples of electrons up to 125 GeV which deposit energy in both the scintillating and Cherenkov fibres. The NN input uses five kinematic variables (energy, x, y, z coordinates and the fibre type) scaled up by the multiplicity (number of hits). Figure 2 shows the hit multiplicity as a function of the electron energy as well as the layer network structure, which halves the number of nodes between successive layers. The difference and correlation between the predicted and true electron energies are shown in Fig. 3, where the energy resolution σ_E is taken as the Gaussian width of the former. The variation of σ_E/E as a function of the true energy E is also shown, where the energy resolution for the 10-layer DNN is significantly worse than just summing all the energy deposits to get the total energy. Doubling the number of DNN layers to 20 (but keeping the same number of nodes) substantially improves the performance, however it is still not as good as using simple energy estimates for energies above 20 GeV or so. It is thought that this is happening because the NN needs to learn various physics processes that are normally dealt with by traditional reconstruction techniques, such as track fitting for the electrons bending in the drift chamber magnetic field and corrections for bremsstrahlung radiation. Also, knowledge of the detector layout will restrict the possible cluster start and end positions, since they should all point back to the interaction point. The DNN is not able to perform these preliminary reconstruction tasks, which limits its ability to improve the measured energies.

Fig.2 Electron hit multiplicity distribution (left) and the DNN layer structure (right).

Fig.3 DNN electron energy resolution: (a) the difference between the predicted and true energies, (b) their correlation and (c) the fractional energy resolution σ_E/E versus true energy E . The reference line is from [9].

2.1.2 CNN Approach

The memory issues encountered when processing all the fibres for the DNN training motivated investigation of the performance of a CNN which has a VGG-like architecture. This contains five convolutional 2D layers represented as 100x100 arrays in ϕ - θ space spanning the calorimeter volume, where ϕ (θ) is the azimuthal (polar) angle and each array separately stores either the total energy or the x, y or z coordinates associated to the scintillation or Cherenkov fibres. During training, the 2D layers are flattened to create three denser layers which then provide the NN output, and both maximum and average pooling methods were tested.

As was found for the DNN, the initial CNN training was not able to fully reconstruct the electron position nor energy in the calorimeter on its own, owing to its lack of knowledge about the preliminary

reconstruction steps that need to be done beforehand. To try to remedy this, energy deposits were collected into proto clusters outside the CNN and their centroid positions were then used as reference points for the training, with the input using the hit energies as well as the relative distances between the hit positions and centroids. Figure 4 shows the scatter plots of the predicted versus true electron angles for the CNN without and with proto clustering, where we see that the angular resolution significantly improves for the latter. However, we still see that the predicted average angles are always larger than the true values, meaning that the CNN does not significantly improve the angular resolution compared to simply using the proto clusters.

Fig.4 The correlation between the CNN-predicted and true cluster angles of electrons without and with proto-clustering applied, as well as the relationship between the centroid predicted angles and their true values.

Figure 5 shows the electron energy resolution for the CNN, comparing different energy summation scenarios depending on whether a selection is made on the cluster radial distance DR, which shows relatively good agreement between the CNN and the simple summation estimates for a given DR choice.

Fig.5 The energy resolution for electron clusters reconstructed with the CNN using the summed energy with/without requiring a selection on the radial distance (DR). Reference line is from [9].

2.1.3 Outcomes

The main conclusion from this work is that we cannot use simple neural networks to completely reconstruct particle showers in the dual-readout calorimeter on their own without first using traditional reconstruction methods. For example, the NN training is not able to replicate the track fitting of electrons bending in the drift chamber magnetic field before they enter the calorimeter. Preliminary tracks and proto cluster candidates must first be found and only then should NNs be used to refine and improve the reconstruction.

Given the current state of this work integration with Pandora is delayed until a more performant reconstruction chain is available.

3 APRIL FOR HADRONIC JETS

APRIL, the algorithm for particle reconstruction (of hadronic jets) for the ILC, is being developed for the International Large Detector (ILD) semi-digital hadronic calorimeter (SDHCAL). Figure 6 shows a prototype of the SDHCAL along with a schematic of its layout in the ILD. APRIL is based on the ARBOR algorithm [10] which assumes a tree-like topology when reconstructing energy clusters in the calorimeter and uses a cluster splitting algorithm with minimum spanning trees for energy reconstruction (AMSTER). We also report on the energy calibration studies that have been done and the progress that has been made in implementing APRIL into the Pandora framework.

Fig. 6 Prototype of the SDHCAL (left) and the ILD geometry layout (right).

3.1 ALGORITHM DEVELOPMENT

The APRIL workflow [11] begins with track-driven clustering, where clusters are started from hits (energy deposits) located near the extrapolation of tracks into the calorimeter, as shown in Fig. 7. The showers are reconstructed as spatial trees which connect neighbouring hits together, with the connections cleaned up to only have one remaining backward connection per hit. Spatial trees are merged until the total energy of the cluster is equal to the measured track energy. Cluster splitting is achieved with AMSTER, which uses the Boost Graph library to implement the minimum spanning tree logic. The cluster hits are used to create graphs which each contain a set of vertices and edges. For each graph, the spanning tree is the subset of edges that connects all the vertices which minimises the total sum of the weights (hit energies). These can then be used to refine the clusters.

Fig. 7 a) Clustering procedure for APRIL and b) the cleanup of connecting hits inside clusters.

Fig. 8 AMSTER reconstruction of a simulation of a 30 GeV charged pion (red simulated and blue reconstructed) with a 10 GeV neutral kaon (green simulated and yellow reconstructed) separated by 20 cm inside a prototype SDHCAL volume.

Tests for APRIL have been performed using a standalone Geant4 prototype simulation of the SDHCAL. Figure 8 shows an example reconstruction of clusters from one 30 GeV charged pion and one 10 GeV neutral kaon, where most of the energy deposits are correctly assigned to the correct particles apart from those around the outer edge of the charged pion shower. Further improvements to the algorithm need to be made, such as improving AMSTER’s capability to separate out clusters from neighbouring neutral particles as well as reducing the required number of graph edges to make

it more efficient. Including detector timing information would also give the capability to perform 4D calorimetry (3D positions with time), which has the potential to improve the performance of APRIL further.

3.2 ENERGY CALIBRATION

A crucial aspect for the SDHCAL is that the reconstructed particle shower and jet energies need to be accurately measured. Using simulation samples generated with the ILC DIRAC grid, energy calibration studies have been done using photons and neutral hadrons to optimise the SDHCAL energy resolution for di-jet reconstruction.

Figure 9 shows the calibration curves relating the reconstructed to the simulated particle energy for single photons in the electromagnetic calorimeter (ECAL) and neutral kaons in the SDHCAL, where the latter needs an extra correction scaling factor due to the particle’s incident angle. Figure 10 shows the corrected energy scaling for the SDHCAL when the incidence angle is taken into account.

Fig. 9 Reconstructed versus simulated particle energy for single photons in the ECAL and neutral kaons in the SDHCAL. The vertical error bars represent the width of the reconstructed cluster energy distributions.

Fig. 10. Reconstructed versus simulated particle energy for neutral kaons in the SDHCAL before and after corrections due to the particle incidence angle have been applied.

3.3 PANDORA FRAMEWORK

The software development has been split into three packages with their own GitHub repositories. The first is APRILContent, which contains APRIL components that can be used by Pandora; the second is SDHCALContent, which performs the energy calibrations; and DDMarlinPandora is used to link both packages together into a specific version of the Pandora framework. Work is now underway to integrate these into the Key4hep software stack.

4 DUNE NEAR DETECTOR

We now summarise the work that has been done to develop Pandora neutrino-interaction reconstruction algorithms for the DUNE Near Detector (ND) [12]. Apart from AIDAInnova work, this research topic includes contributions from other members of the DUNE collaboration.

Fig. 11 Design layout of the ND complex (left) and one of the prototype ND-LAr modules (right). The complex includes SAND (System for on-Axis Neutrino Detection) as well as two argon detectors (gaseous ND-GAr and liquid ND-LAr) that can move in and out of the neutrino beam (for on- and off-axis measurements).

The role of the ND is to characterise the initial state of the neutrino beam for comparisons with measurements at the Far Detector (located in South Dakota), which is then used to extract neutrino oscillation parameters. The core component of the ND is an ArgonCube design [13] which will contain a seven-by-five array of 1m x 1m x 3m LAr modules, each instrumented with two liquid argon time-projection chambers (LArTPCs) that use pixels instead of traditional wires to detect the ionisation charge deposits from the interacting particles. This innovative technology allows us to create 3D neutrino interaction images by combining the pixel signals with the drift (time) coordinate. Figure 11 shows the layout of the ND complex as well as a prototype of one of the LArTPC modules. One of the main challenges for the DUNE ND-LAr is that it will need to deal with a pileup of around 50 neutrinos per beam spill (occurring every 1.2 seconds) due to its closeness to the Long Baseline Neutrino Facility (LBNF) target station which will produce the neutrino beam.

The AIDAinnova project has been vital for the creation of a Pandora reconstruction for the DUNE ND. It facilitated the implementation of the LArRecoND package, which interfaces Pandora algorithms to the ND simulation, and is how existing Pandora LArTPC algorithms can be tested, deployed, benchmarked and optimised for the ND. The creation and continued maintenance of LArRecoND, under AIDAinnova, has anchored the Pandora DUNE ND project and has helped it to grow and gain significant momentum. An international team comprising more than five institutions is coalescing around the work seeded by AIDAinnova, ultimately aiming to deliver a fully bespoke and optimised Pandora ND reconstruction for DUNE's physics programme.

The research outcomes for the DUNE ND Pandora work from this project can be split up into four main areas: i) the development of 3D reconstruction algorithms, ii) the application of deep learning to find neutrino interaction vertices, iii) using hierarchy tools to store the PFO outputs and perform truth matching in Monte Carlo samples containing multiple neutrino interactions, and iv) the creation of Common Analysis Files (CAFs) which is needed for DUNE neutrino physics analyses.

4.1 3D RECONSTRUCTION DEVELOPMENTS

Traditionally, the 3D information of particles interacting inside LArTPCs are reconstructed by combining three 2D projection views (U, V, W). For the DUNE ND, the 3D pixel technology chosen for the LArTPCs means that we can use native 3D space points right from the start of the reconstruction chain, and so we have endeavoured to develop algorithms inside the LArRecoND package to take advantage of this. However, it was not possible to fully convert all the useful neutrino reconstruction algorithms that already exist in Pandora's LArContent package (these require 2D projection information) within the project timeframe, and so these are reused as needed by converting the 3D space points into 2D projection views. The run application for LArRecoND first reads the input event information and LAr geometry layout, then calls a sequence of Pandora algorithms that reconstruct the events in stages (steered by XML parameter files) and writes the final PFOs to an output file. Each input file contains the charge deposits in the LAr volume which are used to create the CaloHits for the Pandora algorithms, and the truth information for Monte Carlo simulation samples is processed using MCParticle objects.

Initially, a pre-processing algorithm is run over the input 3D CaloHits to make sure they have a minimum charge (deposited energy) and are all contained inside the LAr volume. Next, a simple clustering method is used to combine nearby CaloHits together (within 0.5 cm) to create preliminary 3D clusters. This is followed by a range of LArContent cluster-refining algorithms: applying longitudinal and transverse associations or extensions, handling gaps, splitting branches and kinks, and consolidating track-like clusters. These use 2D coordinates of the form $(x, 0, z)$, which effectively means that the y value of each 3D CaloHit is currently ignored during the refining steps. The shapes of the resulting clusters are then checked to see if they correspond to clear track candidates, and nearby tracks are merged. The U, V and W views of the 3D clusters (tracks or showers) are then made and stored as 2D cluster lists, which are passed to the neutrino reconstruction algorithms in LArContent. This finds the neutrino interaction vertices, further improves the tracks and showers, and uses a boosted-decision tree, developed for reconstructing particles in the ProtoDUNE single phase detector [4], to finally create the PFOs for the neutrino events, where any 2D projection information is transformed back into 3D.

Pandora’s performance for reconstructing isolated neutrino interactions in the DUNE ND-LAr is of a broadly similar quality to that obtained for MicroBooNE [2] and ProtoDUNE [4], however there are cases where clusters that are clearly separated in the vertical y direction are not correctly identified due to this information being ignored at the cluster refining stage. This is illustrated in Fig 12, where the right image shows (red) clusters that are separated along the y projection which are combined into a single cluster. To address this problem, the 2D algorithms used for this step need to be updated to use the full 3D information by including the y coordinates.

Fig.12 Preliminary 3D reconstruction of simulated single neutrino interactions in a 2x2 region of the DUNE ND-LAr. Images from L. Whitehead (University of Cambridge, UK).

A major issue for the DUNE ND is that we expect a pile-up of around 50 neutrinos interacting per second in the LAr volume during normal beam operations, due to its closeness with the LBNF target facility. To deal with this, we have begun to develop an algorithm that splits up the CaloHits into slices to reconstruct the individual neutrinos, where one slice corresponds to one neutrino interaction. Each slice is a collection of CaloHits that are clustered together from track and shower candidates that satisfy topological constraints without first assuming any vertices. The neutrino vertices are then added to each slice which also refines the PFOs that have been previously reconstructed. Figure 13 shows an illustration of the 2D projection views of the reconstruction of simulated pile-up neutrino interactions, where each slice is represented by a different colour. Broadly speaking, the slicing technique is showing promise, however much more work is needed to improve its performance, such as reducing the number of cases where particles from different neutrino interactions can appear in the same slice.

Fig. 13 Projection views of the preliminary reconstruction of multiple neutrino interactions in a simulation of the DUNE ND-LAr, where the colours denote different slices. Images from B. Howard (York University, Canada).

4.2 DEEP LEARNING VERTEXING

The reconstruction of neutrino events depends crucially on the correct identification of the interaction vertices, since they tell us where the clusters (tracks and showers) should originate from. The PyTorch deep learning library is used to find neutrino interaction vertices for the DUNE Far Detector Pandora reconstruction [14], and we are using the same approach for DUNE ND-LAr.

First, the SpacePoint input files of simulated single neutrino interactions are processed to produce U, V and W 2D projection images (in CSV format) for each event inside the full ND-LAr volume. These images are then used to train the deep learning network on GPU-accelerated hardware, with the resulting parameters from the first-pass training stored in a PyTorch output file. A second training pass is then made on the same simulated event sample using information from the first pass, but this time each event image is zoomed in by a factor of two to focus on just the true neutrino vertex region, with the results again stored in another PyTorch output file. This procedure, performed using python notebooks available in the LArRecoND package, is followed for each of the U, V and W views. The training output files are then used by the DVerteXingAlgorithm in Pandora's LArContent package, which interfaces to the LibTorch C++ deep learning library, to predict the position of neutrino vertices based on the 2D projection images of each input event.

Figure 14 shows the residual (reconstructed - true) vertex distributions for single muon neutrino events simulated in the DUNE ND-LAr using an ArgonCube geometry that has a total volume of $7 \times 5 \times 3 \text{ m}^3$. The resolution is around 3 mm for the x, y and z axes with no significant biases, although the z distribution has a longer tail on the right hand side since this corresponds to the neutrino beam direction.

Fig 14: Residual vertex distributions (reconstructed - true) for simulated single muon-neutrinos in the DUNE ND-LA ArgonCube geometry using LibTorch deep learning vertexing.

Fig. 15 Reconstruction efficiency for muons, protons and charged pions versus the number of hits (on a log scale) comparing the MicroBooNE state vector machine (SVM) and DUNE ND deep learning (DLVtx) vertexing algorithms.

Figure 15 shows the efficiencies of reconstructing muons, protons and charged pions in a simulated sample of single muon-neutrino interactions in the ND-LAr as a function of the number of generated hits, comparing the vertexing algorithm used by MicroBooNE with the new deep learning one that has been trained for the DUNE ND. Overall, their relative performance is very similar, however the deep learning algorithm improves the reconstruction efficiency for particles with lower numbers of hits, especially protons which typically do not travel very far from the neutrino vertex.

4.3 HIERARCHY TOOLS

The Pandora validation algorithm that calculates reconstruction efficiencies and purities, such as those shown in Fig. 15, can only be used for events that contain just one neutrino interaction (along with any embedded cosmic rays). It cannot process events containing multiple neutrinos, which is the scenario that will occur for the DUNE ND-LAr due to its proximity to the LBNF target facility. To avoid this problem, a set of hierarchy tools has been developed for Pandora to calculate pattern recognition metrics for any number of neutrino interactions inside a given event.

The hierarchy is essentially a collection of tree-like structures, where each tree starts with a given neutrino PFO as the primary node. The direct products of each neutrino interaction are then set as the outputs of this node. These descendent particles become new nodes if they themselves decay or interact to produce other particles. The result is a linked set of nodes which represents the full interaction history starting with the primary neutrino node, and the full hierarchy contains of all the primary nodes. Folding can also be performed if requested, which collapses some or all the descendant nodes onto their parent or primary nodes; the primary option will fold the hierarchy back to primary particles (the neutrino and its direct descendants) while the dynamic setting will keep secondary particle information but will combine PFOs from elastic scatters into their parent nodes.

Two hierarchies can be created, one for the reconstructed PFOs and the other for the Monte Carlo truth particles, and they can be matched together to provide performance metrics such as efficiencies and purities for the reconstruction. Using primary hierarchy folding, we have verified that these metrics agree within statistical uncertainties with the MicroBooNE-like validation output for simulated event samples containing single neutrino interactions, such as those shown in Fig. 15. We are now in a position to quantify Pandora's performance for reconstructing multiple neutrinos in the DUNE ND-LAr when the official simulation samples become available.

4.4 COMMON ANALYSIS FILES

DUNE neutrino physics analyses use CAFs, which are ROOT files [15] that contain all the summary information from the reconstruction, as well as the Monte Carlo truth for simulated samples. We have developed an analysis algorithm that allows us to create Pandora CAFs for the DUNE ND-LAr using hierarchy tools with dynamic folding. It loops over each reconstructed primary neutrino and stores all the relevant PFO information for both itself as well as all its descendants. Both track and shower variables are stored for the 3D cluster associated to each reconstructed PFO, as well as the truth information for its best matched MCParticle, if it exists. The ND-LAr simulation (and data) production now includes collaboration-approved Pandora CAFs, which will benefit all DUNE neutrino physics studies.

5 SUMMARY

We have reported on the research outcomes for adding state-of-the-art PFAs into the Pandora software toolkit for three main detector themes, namely the promising technology of dual-readout calorimeters for FCC-ee, improving the reconstruction of hadronic jets for the future ILC, and using new 3D-readout technology for LAr detectors in neutrino experiments. For the topic of dual-readout calorimeters, an attempt was made to develop a machine-learning algorithm that completely reconstructs particle jets, thereby improving their energy resolution. However, it was found to be too challenging, and already solved, traditional reconstruction methods such as track fitting, preliminary clustering and matching tracks to clusters must first be done before neural networks are used to improve the reconstruction. We also reported on the research done for APRIL, which is being developed for reconstructing hadronic jets in the SDHCAL for the ILD. This work included energy calibration studies as well as developments to include APRIL into the Pandora toolkit. Finally, we described the research done to develop 3D algorithms for the reconstruction of neutrino interactions in the DUNE ND-LAr, which are available in Pandora's LArRecoND package. This work included using deep learning to find neutrino interaction vertices, as well as the implementation of collaboration-approved CAFs using hierarchy tools which will be used for DUNE neutrino physics analyses.

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ANNEX: GLOSSARY

Acronym	Definition
PFA	Particle Flow Algorithm
PFO	Particle Flow Object
DNN	Deep Neural Network
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
APRIL	Algorithm for Particle Reconstruction for the ILC
ILC	International Linear Collider
ILD	International Large Detector
SDHCAL	Semi-digital Hadronic Calorimeter
DUNE	Deep Underground Neutrino Experiment
LBNF	Long-Baseline Neutrino Facility
ND-LAr	Near Detector (filled with) Liquid Argon
LArTPC	Liquid Argon Time Projection Chamber
CAF	Common Analysis File (or Format)